

Dosimetry-driven alpha emitter selection for radioligand therapy: Is daughter translocation a significant safety concern?

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The first long-term safety data with a ²¹²Pb-labelled radiopharmaceutical reported significant renal adverse events beyond two years of follow-up. Understanding pharmacokinetic drivers of doses for alpha-emitting radioligand therapy (RLT) is critical to optimizing molecules. We aimed to compare the dosimetry and therapeutic index (TI) of a single pharmaceutical, rhPSMA-10.1, labelled with ²²⁵Ac or ²¹²Pb, using human pharmacokinetic data.

Methods: Dosimetry from a Phase 1 trial of [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-rhPSMA-10.1 in 13 patients was used to generate time-activity curves for tumors and organs-at-risk. These were used to model [²²⁵Ac]Ac-rhPSMA-10.1 and [²¹²Pb]Pb-rhPSMA-10.1 dosimetry by substituting the physical half-life and decay properties of ¹⁷⁷Lu with the alpha-emitters'. Absorbed doses and TIs were calculated. The impact of daughter radionuclide translocation on organ doses and TIs was modelled.

Results: To deliver 5Gy_(RBE5) to tumors, a ~29-fold higher administered activity of ²¹²Pb was required vs ²²⁵Ac (131 MBq versus 4.6 MBq). At this tumor dose, the activity of ²¹²Pb resulted in 2.5-fold and 2.2-fold higher absorbed doses to kidneys and salivary glands vs ²²⁵Ac. Consequently, ²²⁵Ac demonstrated an improved TI, with a ~3-fold higher tumor:kidney dose ratio (9.85 versus 3.36) and a ~2.2-fold higher tumor:salivary gland ratio (15.9 versus 7.1). When modeling a worst-case scenario for daughter translocation, ²²⁵Ac maintained a superior TI. Importantly, based on rhPSMA-10.1's pharmacokinetics, to achieve 120Gy_(RBE5) to tumors would result in 12.1Gy_(RBE5) and 35.7Gy_(RBE5) delivered to the kidneys for ²²⁵Ac and ²¹²Pb, respectively. Modeling daughter translocation, these values become 39.1Gy_(RBE5) and 114.3Gy_(RBE5), respectively, which may explain recently reported safety data from ²¹²Pb-labelled RLT.

Conclusions: The physical half-life of ²²⁵Ac is better suited to rhPSMA-10.1's pharmacokinetics than the shorter half-life ²¹²Pb. This results in enhanced TI for [²²⁵Ac]Ac-rhPSMA-10.1, delivering lower absorbed doses to organs-at-risk for a fixed tumor dose. ²¹²Pb-labelling may lead to high renal absorbed doses driven by demetallation.

1. Introduction

Imaging emissions secondary to radioligand therapy (RLT) offers a unique ability to provide quantitative estimates of the exposure to radioactivity of each tissue in humans, permitting the calculation of estimated absorbed doses to tumors and normal tissues. Currently, a range of novel RLTs are being explored for numerous targets using both

beta and alpha-emitters. Specifically, there is significant interest in alpha-emitting radionuclides due to their high linear energy transfer and short range, which causes dense complex ionization tracks when damaging DNA [1]. However, performing quantitative radiation dosimetry with the two most available alpha emitters (²²⁵Ac and ²¹²Pb) is challenging given their emission characteristics and complex decay chains (Supplemental Fig. 2). In addition, the dislocation of daughter

Abbreviations: (TAC), Time-Activity Curve; (TI), Therapeutic Index; (IA), Injected Activity; (MIRD), Medical Internal Radiation Dose.

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radionuclides for both alpha-emitters and subsequent deposition around the body—“translocation”—complicates the estimation of absorbed dose.

The use of a “surrogate” radionuclide with excellent imaging properties (e.g. ^{177}Lu , ^{111}In) is a common strategy to assess the pharmacokinetics and radiation dosimetry of a novel RLT prior to committing to larger trials exploring safety and efficacy. The data generated can also be used to assess which alpha-emitting radionuclides may offer the best balance of dose delivered to tumors and to normal tissue, despite the inability to make direct observations with the radionuclides under consideration due to lack of suitable emissions for imaging.

Fundamentally, it is accepted that an ideal agent would deliver all of its absorbed dose to the tumor and none to normal tissue. In reality, it is unavoidable that some radiation dose will be delivered to normal tissue via the expression of the target of interest (“on-target”) and then through exposure to radioactivity from the distribution, metabolism, and excretion that comes with delivering a RLT parenterally (“off-target”). Given this, we can define a putative Therapeutic Index (TI) as the ratio of absorbed dose to the tumor versus absorbed dose to key organs-at-risk. Currently, there is significant scientific debate regarding which radionuclides are optimal for therapeutic use [2]. These discussions often center around the physical properties of the radionuclide in relation to radiobiology, considering biologically effective dose, crossfire effects and range in tissue, as well as the physical half-life [3].

However, the interplay between physical radionuclide half-life and the specific pharmacokinetics of a novel molecule has, surprisingly, rarely been modelled or documented in terms of eventual optimization of therapeutic potential [4]. Here, using a novel human dataset from a recently performed Phase 1 trial with [^{177}Lu]Lu-rhPSMA-10.1 (NCT05413850), we explore the use of two commercially available alpha-emitting radionuclides (^{225}Ac and ^{212}Pb) and the impact that switching out the ^{177}Lu for either of them would have on the estimated absorbed doses and the TI [5,6].

For radiopharmaceuticals labelled with ^{225}Ac or ^{212}Pb , it is understood that decays of the parent radionuclide can lead to dislocation of daughters and subsequent untargeted deposition of “free” daughters throughout the body, colloquially known as “translocation”. Importantly, normal organ doses and therefore therapeutic ratios are sensitive to dislocation and translocation of daughters. In the case of ^{225}Ac , dislocation of daughters happens in ~100% of decays due to the recoil effect, whereas in the case of ^{212}Pb dislocation occurs via chemical interactions due to changes in charge, often referred to as demetallation. This demetallation is thought to occur anywhere from ~36% to ~5% of the time depending on the study and source [5,7,8]. Data from human trials has confirmed that ^{212}Pb demetallation occurs in PSMA-targeting radioligands [9]. The impact of dislocation and translocation of daughters on absorbed doses is difficult to determine, but data presented using a different novel ^{225}Ac -labelled PSMA-targeting small molecule imply almost no translocation occurs from or to target lesions in mice [10,11]. In this analysis by Zitzmann-Kolbe et al., biodistribution data was collected from tumors, kidneys and salivary glands at a range of timepoints. The samples were measured in a gamma counter immediately following sacrifice and many hours later, when secular equilibrium with daughters was in place. As such, the excess or missing ^{221}Fr and ^{213}Bi versus expected equilibrium activities could be measured. The lack of translocation to or from the tumor suggests the majority of translocation happens due to decays occurring in plasma. These data resulted in increase to the kidney dose by a factor of ~3.2 and salivary dose by a factor of 4, with no change in tumour dose. Herein, these factors are referred to as “amplification factors”. While it is possible to simulate biodistribution and dosimetric impact from daughters using ICRP biokinetic models, previous studies have demonstrated that these models are highly sensitive to compartment assumptions [12]. Therefore, as an alternative approach, in this work the amplification factor measured in mice is used as a base case. Of note, the increased detection of ^{213}Bi in salivary glands and kidneys in these animal models, presumably

following dislocation from parent, aligns with subsequent pre-clinical investigations [13], although it is unknown if this is truly free ionic bismuth or some other complex.

2. Methods

2.1. Dosimetry

Using dosimetry data from a Phase 1 trial of novel RLT, [^{177}Lu]Lu-rhPSMA-10.1, in 13 patients with metastatic castration-resistant prostate cancer [NCT05413850], time–activity curves were generated for the first treatment cycle (Cycle 1) for each of the 13 participants [14]. Ethics approval for study NCT05413850 was provided by Advarra dated 21-Jul-2024 (4923774) and METC-Oost Nederland dated 01-Nov-2023 (NL83153.091.22). Patient details are described in [Supplemental Table 2](#). These data were acquired with 4 time-point SPECT/CT scans at 3, 24, 48, and 168 h post-administration. In addition, radioactive blood samples were acquired at 0.5, 1.5, 4, 24, and 48 h post-administration. The scanners and gamma counters used to acquire these data were calibrated prior to imaging. From the SPECT/CT scans, activities were measured within volumes of interest in tumors and normal tissues at each of these time-points and cumulative activities calculated for tumors and organs-at-risk, similar to Nagarajah et al. [14]. Full details on dosimetry methods have been previously described, also in Nagarajah et al. [14].

For the purposes of modelling, dosimetry data acquired above was corrected for physical decay of ^{177}Lu before applying the physical decay constant for ^{225}Ac and ^{212}Pb . Thus, the activity within the regions of interest of delineable normal tissues and tumors from all imaging time-points as well as activities measured in blood samples were extrapolated from the 6.7-day half-life of ^{177}Lu to the half-life of 9.9-days of ^{225}Ac and 10.64 h of ^{212}Pb . In this way, effective half-lives for tissues were obtained assuming identical biological half-lives between different radionuclides, given the pharmaceutical was unchanged. Cumulative activities were calculated by integrating under these curves, and absorbed doses were calculated according to S-values calculated using the MIRD formulation (MIRDcalc internal dose calculation software v20220504) [15]. Therapeutic indices were then determined as the ratios of absorbed doses (Gy/Gy) as shown in Equation (1):

$$TI = \frac{\bar{D}_{\text{tumour}}}{\bar{D}_{\text{OAR}}} \quad (1)$$

Where \bar{D} is the absorbed dose to the *tumor* or *organ-at-risk* (OAR). MIRD S-values accounted for the entire decay chain including all daughters with beta and/or alpha emissions.

As this was a novel prostate-specific membrane antigen (PSMA)-targeted RLT, organs-at-risk were selected as those which are of significant concern due to known dose deposition from the expression of PSMA and elimination routes. These included the salivary glands and the kidneys. The data were plotted using LabPlot Version 2.10.0, a C++ compiled data plotting software. Data was fitted with mono- or bi-exponential functions selected using statistical tests as recommended by Ivashchenko et al. [16]. Goodness of fit was also assessed with both a visual check and minimizing the absolute Akaike information criterion (AIC).

These fits were then integrated to a 720-h cut-off using LabPlot2's integral analysis tool (Simpson's 3-point method). For calculation of absorbed doses, the S-values listed in [Supplemental Table 3](#) were used for the associated tissues and the commonly used relative biological effectiveness value of 5 (RBE5) was used to account for the increased cytotoxicity of alpha particles versus gamma or beta radiation.

2.2. Translocation

Using the assumption that absorbed dose increase, previously

Table 1

Inputs and outputs for amplification factor calculation.

Input - $P_{ab(Pb)}$	Output - Amplification Factor of Pb
2 x $P_{ab(Ac)}$	5.4
3 x $P_{ab(Ac)}$	7.6
4 x $P_{ab(Ac)}$	9.8

mentioned amplification factor, is a result of decays occurring in free plasma, scales linearly, and it is accurate for ^{225}Ac , the known plasma half-life of [^{177}Lu]Lu-rhPSMA-10.1 acquired with radioactive blood sampling on phase 1 patients was used to calculate the proportion of total potential decays which occur in plasma for both [^{225}Ac]Ac-rhPSMA-10.1 and [^{212}Pb]Pb-rhPSMA-10.1. This was done by first adjusting for the physical half-lives of the alpha-emitters to simulate plasma-washout curves from the known [^{177}Lu]Lu-rhPSMA-10.1 washout. Specifically, the effective decay constant of the alpha emitter in plasma (λ_{eff}) was calculated from the measured ^{177}Lu washout as described in equation (2):

$$\lambda_{eff}(\alpha) = [\lambda_{eff}(\text{Lu}) - \lambda_{phys}(\text{Lu})] + \lambda_{phys}(\alpha) \quad (2)$$

Integrating under these curves out to 7 days gives the cumulative activity in plasma (\tilde{A}_{pl}) which gives the total number of decays occurring in plasma, while integrating under physical decay gave the total potential decays injected (\tilde{A}_{pot}) as outlined in equations 3 and 4:

$$\tilde{A}_{pl} = IA \int_0^7 e^{x-\lambda_{eff}} dx \quad (3)$$

$$\tilde{A}_{pot} = IA \int_0^7 e^{x-\lambda_{phys}} dx \quad (4)$$

Where IA is the simulated injected activity, x is the time in days, λ_{eff} is the effective decay constant of the radioligand in plasma, and λ_{phys} is the physical decay constant of the radionuclide in question. Seven days was selected to coincide with contamination restrictions on [^{177}Lu]Lu-rhPSMA-10.1 and therefore expected to capture the entirety of washout period. We can then define further variables in equations 4 and 5:

$$P_d = \frac{\tilde{A}_{pl}}{\tilde{A}_{pot}} \quad (4)$$

$$P_{ab} = P_d \times R_{pr} \times L_{dis} \quad (5)$$

Where P_d is the proportion of potential injected decays occurring in plasma, P_{ab} is the proportion of potential injected absorbed dose dislocated in plasma, R_{pr} is the proportional dose contribution from progeny. This can be estimated using ratios of S-values and yields for different proportions of the parent decay chain. For example, the ^{225}Ac decay chain is given in Supplemental Fig. 2. Using MIRDCalc values for kidney, the S-value for ^{225}Ac emissions from decay to ^{221}Fr is 8.08 mGy/MBq*h (MIRDCalc ref). In this case, R_{pr} would be 0.79. As different organs have different R_{pr} , an average R_{pr} of approximately 0.75 for ^{225}Ac and 0.98 for ^{212}Pb have been used. L_{dis} is the proportion of decays that lead to dislocation (1 for ^{225}Ac , assumed demetallation rate for ^{212}Pb).

If we then assume that the amplification factor detected by Zitzmann-Kolbe et al. is proportional to P_{ab} , we can identify the point at which P_{ab} is identical for both ^{212}Pb and ^{225}Ac as the point at which the amplification factor would be equal. We can also use the relative differences of P_{ab} to scale the amplification factor of ^{212}Pb accordingly for various assumed demetallation rates. In this way the amplification factor for ^{212}Pb is calculated with equation (6):

$$AF_{(Pb)} = \left[\frac{P_{ab(Pb)}}{P_{ab(Ac)}} (AF_{(Ac)} - 1) \right] + 1 \quad (6)$$

The constants are required because only the daughter dose contribution should be scaled, not the entire factor including the parent dose. Some example scenarios are given in Table 1.

This also relies upon the assumption that the uptake into various organs of free ^{213}Bi and free ^{212}Bi are identical. It should be noted that, as the half-life of ^{212}Bi is longer than that of ^{213}Bi (60.5 vs 45.6 min), this will likely underestimate the amount of ^{212}Bi decaying in key normal tissues like kidney and salivary glands. This scaling assumes that the biological component of plasma washout is identical between ^{212}Pb - and ^{225}Ac -labelled radioligand. The uncertainty on these amplification

Fig. 1. Example tumor and kidney time-activity curves with best-fits from a single patient simulating different radionuclides based on different physical half-lives but otherwise identical pharmacokinetics. Panel A shows kidney TACs, Panel B shows tumor TACs.

Fig. 2. Required activity injected in MBq to achieve an average absorbed tumor dose of 5Gy(RBE5).

factors is large and difficult to determine. However, it will consist of uncertainty in the initial measurement, in the scaling to humans with different pharmacokinetics, branching ratios and the plasma half-life used to do the scaling. Uncertainty in the plasma half-life was measured as ± 7.4 min based on standard deviation, which as a percentage is $\pm 5.4\%$ standard error. There is no error given by Zitzmann Kolbe et al. on the dose amplification factor calculated, but as it is established using a similar counting regimen to another study measuring ^{213}Bi , we can estimate a minimum systematic counting error from uncertainties in calibration factors quoted in this similar study [13]. This uncertainty for the ^{213}Bi calibration factor was $\pm 0.062 \text{ Bq}^{-1}$, which as a percentage is $\pm 3.76\%$. Assuming linear propagation of the plasma half-life through to a multiplication of the amplification factor with linear propagation of the calibration factor uncertainty, this gives a minimum uncertainty on the re-calculated amplification factors of

$\pm 9.2\%$. Branching ratio error is negligible in comparison to this value. In reality, this uncertainty is almost certainly dwarfed by the uncertainties in the scaling of biodistribution to humans, but this value is not possible to derive with any level of confidence.

No adjustments accounting for potential injected free $^{221}\text{Fr}/^{213}\text{Bi}$ were made, given that the majority of ^{213}Bi in formulation will be chelated by DTPA and rapidly excreted with minimal dose delivery, and that the contribution from free ^{221}Fr is likely negligible. Due to the faster decay rate for ^{212}Pb and the greater proportion of absorbed dose delivered by ^{212}Pb daughters (approximately 98% versus 75% for ^{225}Ac), if 11% of ^{212}Pb decays lead to demetallation, this results in the same P_{ab} for $[^{212}\text{Pb}]\text{Pb-rhPSMA-10.1}$ as for $[^{225}\text{Ac}]\text{Ac-rhPSMA-10.1}$, therefore an equal level of dose increase as occurs with ^{225}Ac . Given the range and uncertainty of demetallation rates for ^{212}Pb complexes, we used a value of 11% for simplicity in the example translocation doses

Fig. 3. Modelled absorbed doses. Panel A shows the representative kidney dose for 5Gy(RBE5) tumor dose, panel B shows the salivary gland dose for a 5Gy(RBE5) tumor dose, and panel C shows the achievable tumor dose for a 35Gy(RBE5) kidney dose.

Fig. 4. Modelled translocation doses. Panel A shows the kidney dose for $5\text{Gy}_{(\text{RBE5})}$ tumor dose with translocation, panel B shows the salivary dose for $5\text{Gy}_{(\text{RBE5})}$ tumor dose with translocation, and panel C shows the tumor dose for a $35\text{Gy}_{(\text{RBE5})}$ kidney dose.

given in the relevant figure (Fig. 4). However, we also investigated the impact of translocation for a “worst case” demetallation rate of 36%, as was demonstrated for DOTA chelators by Mirzadeh et al., given similar DOTA family chelators are in some cases being investigated for ^{212}Pb radioligands in clinical trials [8].

3. Results

The statistical results from model fit testing can be found in the [Supplemental Table 1](#).

An example of curve-fits for tumor and kidney from a single patient included in the study can be found in [Fig. 1](#), simulating different radionuclides according to equation (2). The results demonstrate that, in order to deliver a $5\text{Gy}_{(\text{RBE5})}$ absorbed dose to tumors, a considerably higher (approximately 29-fold) administered activity of ^{212}Pb is required than of ^{225}Ac (Fig. 2). The mean (\pm standard deviation) results being $131 (\pm 106)$ MBq (range: 27–293 MBq) and $4.6 (\pm 4.4)$ MBq (range: 0.7–11.3 MBq), respectively. This approximately 29-fold difference is the result of the notably shorter physical half-life leading to a short effective half-life in tumor, which reduces the area under curve and therefore time-integrated cumulative activity for equivalent administered activities. In addition, compared to ^{225}Ac , the S-value is notably smaller due to fewer alpha emissions per decay for ^{212}Pb .

Assuming no translocation and a target of $5\text{Gy}_{(\text{RBE5})}$ delivered to the tumor, the absorbed doses delivered to the kidney and salivary glands are substantially different between radionuclides (Fig. 3). The higher administered activity of ^{212}Pb required for the $5\text{Gy}_{(\text{RBE5})}$ to the tumor results in a 2.5-fold and 2.2-fold higher delivery of dose to the kidney and salivary glands, respectively. The absorbed dose delivered to tumors for a $35\text{Gy}_{(\text{RBE5})}$ dose to kidneys is 2.9-fold higher for ^{225}Ac than ^{212}Pb (Fig. 3c). These normal-organ absorbed doses also lead to significantly improved TIs for the ^{225}Ac -labelled radiopharmaceutical versus the ^{212}Pb -labelled one. The mean (\pm standard deviation) tumour: kidney absorbed dose ratios were $9.85 (\pm 8.49)$ and $3.36 (\pm 2.79)$, respectively, and for the tumour: salivary absorbed dose ratio they were $15.9 (\pm 12.5)$

and $7.06 (\pm 5.76)$, respectively.

Given the assumed amplification factor for both radionuclides is identical in the translocation modelling as determined by the selected demetallation rate of ^{212}Pb being 11%, the difference between TI for each remains the same. The mean (\pm standard deviation) tumor: kidney absorbed dose ratios in this scenario are $3.08 (\pm 2.65)$ and $1.05 (\pm 0.87)$ for ^{225}Ac and ^{212}Pb , respectively. For ^{212}Pb to match the ^{225}Ac TI under these assumptions when accounting for translocation, less than 1% of ^{212}Pb day must lead to demetallation events. Conversely, with 0% ^{212}Pb demetallation, the tumor: kidney ratios of [^{225}Ac]Ac-rhPSMA-10.1 would be better than [^{212}Pb]Pb-rhPSMA-10.1 if the kidney dose increase due to ^{225}Ac daughter translocation was a factor of 2.93 or less.

In the event that 36% of ^{212}Pb day lead to ^{212}Bi dislocation, the tumor: kidney absorbed dose ratio for [^{212}Pb]Pb-rhPSMA-10.1 would be lowered to 0.39. The comparison is shown in [Supplemental Fig. 1](#).

A systematic review of the only approved PSMA-targeted RLT (Pluvicto/[^{177}Lu]Lu-vipivotide tetraxetan) reports an average absorbed tumor dose of $4.04\text{Gy}/\text{GBq}$ [17]. Assuming an average of 4 out of a maximum of 6 cycles allowed within the product license, we can assume an average cumulative radiation dose to prostate cancer lesions of $\sim 120\text{Gy}$. The impact of attempting to deliver $120\text{Gy}_{(\text{RBE5})}$ to tumors can be seen in the graphical abstract, leading to kidney doses of $28.67 (\pm 31.04)$ and $71.23 (\pm 53.43)$ $\text{Gy}_{(\text{RBE5})}$ for ^{225}Ac and ^{212}Pb , respectively, without translocation and $91.73 (\pm 99.35)$ and $227.92 (\pm 170.99)$ $\text{Gy}_{(\text{RBE5})}$ with the translocation assumptions used in this modeling.

4. Discussion

The calculated absorbed dose coefficients for kidney and lesions without translocation for [^{225}Ac]Ac-rhPSMA-10.1 compare favorably with those calculated by Liubchenko et al. for [^{225}Ac]Ac-PSMA-I&T: $0.27 (\pm 0.08)$ $\text{Gy}_{\text{RBE5}}/\text{MBq}$ vs $0.17 (\pm 0.06)$ $\text{Sv}_{\text{RBE5}}/\text{MBq}$ for kidney, $2.6 (\pm 2.45)$ $\text{Gy}_{\text{RBE5}}/\text{MBq}$ vs $0.36 (\pm 0.1)$ $\text{Sv}_{\text{RBE5}}/\text{MBq}$ for lesions (rhPSMA-10.1 vs I&T) [18]. Similarly comparing [^{212}Pb]Pb-rhPSMA-10.1 to [^{212}Pb]Pb-CA012 absorbed doses calculated by Kratochwil et al.: 0.0243

(± 0.007) Gy_{RBE5}/MBq vs 0.049 Sv_{RBE5}/MBq for kidney, 0.08 (± 0.06) Gy_{RBE5}/MBq vs 0.132 Sv_{RBE5}/MBq for lesions (rhPSMA-10.1 vs CA012) [19]. Using the measured pharmacokinetics of [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-rhPSMA-10.1 in humans, the impact of labelling the pharmaceutical with ²²⁵Ac versus ²¹²Pb was modelled. Due to the short physical half-life and decay properties of ²¹²Pb, notably lower activities of ²²⁵Ac are required compared with ²¹²Pb to achieve clinically meaningful tumor doses. In order to deliver an equivalent dose to tumor, approximately 29-fold more radioactivity is required when considering ²¹²Pb compared with ²²⁵Ac. Even if translocation of daughters is ignored, substantially improved TIs are achieved using ²²⁵Ac versus ²¹²Pb (3-fold higher) due to the long retention in tumor and rapid washout from normal organs of the radiopharmaceutical favoring the longer half-life of ²²⁵Ac. It should be noted that the decrease in tumor dose for identical kidney doses switching from ²²⁵Ac to ²¹²Pb is not equal to the increased kidney dose for equivalent tumor dose, which is a mathematical feature resulting from the method of averaging. When translocation is modelled, unless it is possible to achieve a demetallation rate of <1% of ²¹²Pb day, ²²⁵Ac continues to offer an improved TI.

The impact of translocation for both radionuclides is based on data derived from a radiopharmaceutical with significantly longer plasma half-life than rhPSMA-10.1 [10]. Therefore, normal organ doses from decays occurring in plasma are likely overestimated and the values presented here can be considered a “worst case scenario” for alpha-labelled rhPSMA-10.1. On the other hand, the contribution of translocation from daughters for antibodies, which have significantly longer plasma half-lives than small molecules, such as J591, is likely to be far greater than the contributions estimated here. The contribution of daughter translocation such as “free” Bismuth to normal organ doses is going to be highly sensitive to how the clearance and binding of ²¹²Bi/²¹³Bi differs to the still-bound parent radiopharmaceutical. This may differ in humans from the animal models used to estimate values described in this paper. ICRP indicate preferential kidney uptake of ²¹²Bi in humans, validating the finding of increased kidney absorbed dose [20]. If, in fact, clearance rates of Bismuth are significantly slower than assumed, this may lead to increased marrow exposure rather than kidney exposure as found in this analysis.

The results of this modelling demonstrate the intrinsic importance of combining pharmacokinetics and radiation dosimetry with radionuclide selection. Ideally, these results would be available prior to the selection of the alpha-emitting radionuclide which might be taken into human clinical trials. Importantly, recently reported clinical data from a ²¹²Pb labelled molecule targeting the somatostatin receptor suggested a significant signal for renal toxicity with more than 2 years of follow up data. More than 1 in 3 patients experience some sort of adverse renal event (37%), with 17% experiencing G3 or above adverse renal events [21]. Whilst it is unclear to what extent this is a target-specific phenomenon, this safety signal correlates with the findings of this modelling work and supports the idea that demetallation may be driving the deposition of significant renal absorbed radiation dose.

There are some potential limitations to this work. Integrating TACs to 720 h may introduce bias against ²²⁵Ac, given a small proportion of dose may be delivered after this time-point in exceptional circumstances due to its long half-life. It should also be noted that absorbed dose estimates use an RBE factor for alpha radiation versus gamma or beta radiation. The RBE for alpha used in calculations is 5 and is based on historical in vitro observations [22]. However, there are wide ranges reported for this value and the biological applicability remains unknown in humans [23]. Although, even if this RBE value were not applied, the estimates for activity administered for both ²²⁵Ac and ²¹²Pb would likely increase similarly for both radionuclides and the TIs would remain unchanged. Another aspect of radiobiology not accounted for in this modelling is the impact of dose-rate on biologically effective dose. Dose-rate impact from alpha radiation on the biologically effective dose is currently poorly understood but the literature broadly supports the concept that, given the clustered complex ionization tracks created by

alpha particles, increasing the dose rate is unlikely to meaningfully increase the proportion of cells killed. The literature proposes that the “single-hit” nature of alpha particle damage means that the ultimate fate of the cell is determined by the total dose received, not the timing of its delivery [24–27]. However, the majority of these data are derived from non-physiologically relevant in vitro studies, and further work in radiobiology is required to understand what, if any, impact dose rate has in human patients with metastatic cancer. It is worth noting that if higher dose rates with alpha particles do lead to a greater proportion of cells killed, it may create a higher risk of toxicity in key normal organs given that those dose rates must also apply to binding target receptor expressed in healthy tissue, which is highest in the early hours after injection.

Another limitation of this work is the presumed identical pharmacokinetics of an alpha-emitter labelled version of rhPSMA-10.1, except for physical half-life. It is known that switching ¹⁷⁷Lu for ²²⁵Ac causes small chemical changes in the molecule, so it may be possible that this would impact the pharmacokinetics beyond the physical half-life difference. However, pre-clinical biodistribution data imply similar behavior between the two and it is reasonable to suppose this may extend to a ²¹²Pb-labelled version for the purposes of modelling radiation dosimetry [28].

Additionally, the assumption that dislocated ²¹³Bi and ²¹²Bi behave identically may be overly simplistic. The amplification factor results relied upon in this paper are generated in mice and may therefore not be applicable to humans. The assumption that the proportion of potential absorbed dose dislocated in plasma (P_{ab}) is proportional to amplification factor and the factor scales linearly follows from the presumed identical biodistribution of ²¹²Bi/²¹³Bi and the absolute relative S-values of daughters vs parents. Furthermore, it follows from evidence in pre-clinical models that the overwhelming source of free bismuth is from decays happening during plasma circulation. However, this may be an overly simplistic assumption, for example if there is a significant saturation effect in normal organs. Although, it is difficult to hypothesize that the uptake of free ²¹²Bi and ²¹³Bi in the kidney could become “saturated” given their status as single atoms. Finally, while we have attempted to fairly model for translocation, we have not accounted for the presence of free ²²¹Fr upon administration of the ²²⁵Ac formulation. Although preliminary calculations imply an extremely small contribution to normal tissue dose from this phenomenon, including these contributions would add to the accuracy of the modeling [12]. Further valuable work would be assessing the impact of translocation on red bone marrow absorbed dose, particularly given the uncertainty in renal and plasma clearance of free daughters versus the parent radiopharmaceuticals. It is plausible that given the level of dislocation happening in plasma without isolating dislocated bismuth at sampling from parent-bound radionuclide, absorbed dose calculations from radioactive blood samples assuming secular equilibrium may overestimate red bone marrow doses. This would have to be assessed using radioactive blood samples from humans administered the alpha-labelled radiopharmaceuticals [²²⁵Ac]Ac-rhPSMA-10.1 and [²¹²Pb]Pb-rhPSMA-10.1 in the case such studies were performed.

While the absolute values given in the results will have wider uncertainties than the value presented in methods, conclusions derived from relative differences are still meaningful, given results from both radionuclides will suffer from similar levels of bias & uncertainty.

5. Conclusion

Based on modeling using human pharmacokinetic data from [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-rhPSMA-10.1, we have demonstrated that in this radiopharmaceutical the choice between ²²⁵Ac and ²¹²Pb as alpha-emitters has a profound impact on the agent's TI. The shorter physical half-life and decay properties of ²¹²Pb are poorly matched to the observed pharmacokinetics, leading to a requirement for ~29-fold higher administered activity to achieve the same tumor dose as ²²⁵Ac. This mismatch results in

Key points

QUESTION: Which alpha-emitter should a novel PSMA targeting RLT utilize to maximize absorbed dose delivery to tumors relative to normal tissues such as the kidney?

PERTINENT FINDINGS: Simple adjustments to effective half-lives in tissue from dosimetry data acquired from a novel PSMA targeting radioligand radiolabeled with an easily imaged radionuclide (^{177}Lu) allows theoretical time-activity curves to be plotted for the scenario in which it is labelled with an alpha-emitter. Dosimetry calculations using these time-activity curves and existing data on daughter translocation from ^{225}Ac and ^{212}Pb indicate ^{225}Ac offers superior absorbed dose distribution than ^{212}Pb .

IMPLICATIONS FOR PATIENT CARE: Utilizing ^{225}Ac as an alpha-emitter is likely to deliver an improved balance of absorbed dose to tumors relative to normal healthy tissue than ^{212}Pb . This may improve clinical outcomes when developing rhPSMA-10.1.

a significantly poorer TI for ^{212}Pb , with off-target doses to the kidneys and salivary glands approximately 2- to 3-fold higher than with ^{225}Ac . Even when daughter radionuclide translocation is considered, ^{225}Ac maintains its dosimetric advantage unless the demetallation rate of ^{212}Pb is less than 1%, a level not currently supported by any published clinical literature. Our results suggest that for a molecule with a similar pharmacokinetic profile to rhPSMA-10.1, ^{225}Ac is the preferred alpha-emitter, offering a more favorable balance of tumor-to-normal tissue dose. This study underscores the fundamental principle that radionuclide selection should not be made in isolation but must be rationally driven by the specific pharmacokinetic properties of the targeting molecule to maximize therapeutic outcomes. As this result is demonstrated specifically with rhPSMA-10.1, the absolute values presented for TI and tumor or normal tissue absorbed dose will not be exactly replicated with other radiopharmaceuticals. However, the resulting comparisons between ^{225}Ac and ^{212}Pb are likely generalizable to any radiopharmaceutical with long retention of the vector in tumors relative to normal tissue.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Benjamin Fongenie: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Project administration, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Nathaniel Scott:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Nicolas Chouin:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Ana M. Denis-Bacelar:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Daniel J. Stevens:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization.

Consent for publication

Not Applicable.

Ethical approval and consent to participate

The ongoing phase I/II study ^{177}Lu -rhPSMA-10.1 (NCT05413850) has been performed in line with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by appropriate ethics committees in the US and Netherlands, including Advarra and East Netherlands MEC. Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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No other conflicts of interest exist.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Ben Fongenie reports a relationship with Blue Earth Therapeutics Limited that includes: employment and equity or stocks. Daniel Stevens reports a relationship with Blue Earth Therapeutics Limited that includes: employment and equity or stocks. Nathaniel Scott reports a relationship with Blue Earth Therapeutics Limited that includes: employment and equity or stocks. AMDB was supported by the National Measurement System of the UK Government's Department for Science, Innovation and Technology, and by the project 22HLT03 AlphaMet, funded from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States, where the National Physical Laboratory is funded by UKRI under the UK Government's Horizon Europe Guarantee scheme (no. 10117403). If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. Ana M. Denis-Bacelar is an Editorial Board member of EANM Innovation but was not involved in any way in the evaluation, revision, or decision process of this article.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eanmi.2026.100129>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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